

Preparation of Nitriles and Amides of Benzocaine as Potential Drugs

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α -aminonitriles of the type $\begin{array}{c} R' \\ | \\ R-C-NH.C_6H_4CO_2C_2H_5(4) \\ | \\ CN \end{array}$ have been synthesized from benzocaine and various aldehydes and ketones. These compounds are further converted into the amides of the type,

to study their physiological activities.

BESIDES being a well-known local anaesthetic¹, benzocaine is also reported as antibacterial, fungicidal and antitubercular compound.²⁻⁵ α -Aminonitriles are reported as compounds possessing insecticidal as well as CNS stimulant property.⁶⁻⁹ We therefore synthesized the nitriles of benzocaine as drug potentials for testing antibacterial activity.

The α -aminonitriles of the type,

have been synthesised, where

$R' = CH_3$ or H and
 $R = C_6H_5$; 4- $CH_3O.C_6H_4$; 2- and 4- $Cl.C_6H_4$;
 4- and 3- $O_2N.C_6H_4$; C_4H_3O ; 2- $HO.C_6H_4$;
 3- $CH_3O-4-HOC_6H_3$; 5- $Br-3-CH_3O-4-HO.C_6H_3$;
 C_6H_4 ; 5- $O_2N-3-CH_3O-4-HO.C_6H_2$; 3,4-
 $(CH_3O)_2.C_6H_3$; 6- $Br-3,4-(CH_3O)_2.C_6H_2$;
 $C_6H_5CH = CH$; CH_3 ; $n-C_3H_7$; $iso-C_4H_9$, etc.

The compounds of type (I) are treated with excess of concentrated H_2SO_4 at 0° and allowed to stand for 48 hr at room temperature to get the amides¹⁰ of the following type :

where R and R' are same as described previously. Under these conditions the CN group of the compounds of type (I) was converted into $CONH_2$ group

and not into COOH group. These amides are synthesised to study their antibacterial and anaesthetic activities, because the amides are reported as anaesthetic, antispasmodic, and antibacterial.¹¹⁻¹³

Experimental

Preparation of nitriles of benzocaine¹⁴ (I)

The aldehyde (0.1 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (95%) or methanol (40 ml) and potassium cyanide (0.1 mole) in water (10 ml) was added, followed by glacial acetic acid (0.1 mole). The mixture was stirred mechanically and benzocaine (0.1 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%) or methanol (70 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hr at $25^\circ-30^\circ$. The product separated as crystals in most of the cases but in some cases it was separated when the reaction mixture was poured on ice and was crystallised from ethanol. The physical and analytical data are reported in Table 1.

Hydrolysis of the α -aminonitriles to amides (II)

The α -aminonitrile was treated with excess of concentrated H_2SO_4 at 0° and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 hr. The cyano group of the α -aminonitrile was hydrolysed to give amide group. The resulting amide was separated by diluting the reaction mixture with ice water. The product was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol. The physical and analytical data of these amides are reported in Table 2.

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TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (I)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Molecular Formula	m.p. °C	Required % N	Found % N
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	125	10.00	9.91
2.	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃	110	9.06	9.31
3.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	116	8.90	9.13
4.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	94	8.90	9.02
5.	3-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	136	12.92	13.16
6.	4-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	78	12.92	12.87
7.	C ₄ H ₃ O	H	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	96	10.37	10.25
8.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	183	9.46	9.63
9.	3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	130	8.59	8.74
10.	5-Br-3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₂	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ O ₄	180	6.91	7.06
11.	5-O ₂ N-3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₂	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	168	11.32	11.07
12.	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	H	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	112	8.23	8.18
13.	6-Br-3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₂	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₄	178	7.01	7.09
14.	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	135	9.15	9.01
15.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	77	12.07	11.95
16.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	90	9.97	10.16
17.	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	89	11.39	11.29
18.	n-C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	78	10.77	10.62
19.	iso-C ₄ H ₉	CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	76	10.22	10.36
20.	$\begin{matrix} & R' \\ & \diagdown \\ C \\ & \diagup \\ & R \end{matrix} = C_6H_{10}$		C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	67	10.30	10.44

TABLE 2—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (II)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Molecular Formula	m.p. °C	Required % N	Found % N
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	167	8.80	8.71
2.	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	85	8.53	8.65
3.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₃	90	7.94	8.16
4.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₃	100	7.94	8.07
5.	3-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	140	12.24	12.18
6.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	172	8.38	8.51
7.	5-Br-3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₂	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₅	225(d)	6.62	6.95
8.	5-O ₂ N-3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₂	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₇	86	10.79	10.64
9.	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	H	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	200	7.82	7.97
10.	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH	H	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	125	8.64	8.53
11.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	123	11.20	11.09
12.	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	230(d)	10.61	10.74
13.	n-C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	145(d)	10.08	10.00
14.	iso-C ₄ H ₉	CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	223	9.81	10.06
15.	$\begin{matrix} & R' \\ & \diagdown \\ C \\ & \diagup \\ & R \end{matrix} = C_6H_{10}$		C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	96	9.61	9.89

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